

Sustainability Testing and Environmental Dynamism: Are Corporate Governance with Firm-specific Factors Relevant?

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Abstract

The turbulent environment within which the manufacturing sector operates in Nigeria has led to the closure of several manufacturing companies over the years. To sustain their operations in the face of the dynamic environment, corporate strategies have been inclined to shrink firm sizes and move to cost-advantaged locations outside Nigeria. The development raises the question of the relevance of Corporate Governance (CG) and Firm-Specific Factors (FSF) in addressing the issues affecting the Sustainability of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Manufacturers (FMCGMs) in Nigeria. Thus, the study examined the effect of CG and FSF on the Sustainability of FMCGMs in Nigeria and further interrogated the intervening effects of Environmental Dynamism (EVD) on the interaction between CG, FSF, and the Sustainability of FMCGMs in Nigeria. The study is anchored on the Stakeholder Theory and Dynamic Capabilities Theory. The cross-sectional survey design was employed to obtain data from 432 employees of the FMCGMs in Nigeria. Data collected were analyzed using the PLS-SEM to examine the three-way direct, mediation, and moderation hypotheses. Findings show that CG and FSF have a significant effect on the Sustainability of the selected FMCGMs ($Adj R^2 = 0.878$, $p = 0.000$); EVD Exerted a positive and significant moderating effect on the interaction between CG and Sustainability ($\beta = 0.386$; $p = 0.006$, $Q^2 = 0.290$); EVD was also found to exert a positive and significant mediating effect on the interaction between FSF and Sustainability of the selected FMCGMs ($\beta = 0.396$, $t = 2.919$, $p = 0.004$). The study recommends the need for FMCGMs to pay particular attention to their CG strategy to improve stakeholder loyalty, maintain a flexible FSF configuration, and continuously evaluate how the dynamic environment impacts achieving set targets while establishing policies and actions that continue to align performance to achieving set goals.

Keywords: Environmental dynamism, Dynamic Capability theory, Firm-specific-factors, Manufacturing companies, sustainability

Introduction

Sustainability underscores the need for manufacturing companies to look beyond their profit motives to maintain their going concern. Given that a firm's goodwill should not only be based on fulfilling the

wealth goals of shareholders; instead, how society perceives the firm in terms of social responsibility and environmental performance becomes a critical success factor that could guarantee the firm's going concern. Globally, sustainability issues appear to be more centred around the environmental sustainability dimension. The 2020 global Environmental Performance Index (EPI) ranks Denmark the most environmentally sustainable country globally, with Luxembourg, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom at 2nd, 3rd, and 4th positions, respectively. The United States of America ranks 21 after Malta, Italy, and Canada, with Malta occupying the 20th rank, while Italy and Canada tie for the 18th position. Seychelles tops the list of the most environmentally sustainable sub-Saharan African countries, ranking 38 globally, followed by Gabon, Moraceous, and South Africa at 76, 82, and 95 world rank positions. In West Africa, Burkina Faso, with 38.3 points, tops the West African list of the Global EPI, ranking 112 at the global position; Nigeria stands at the 151 position (out of 180 countries around the world) with 31.0 points (Wendling, Emerson, Sheribinin & Etsy, 2020). This statistic creates a concern for manufacturing activities in Nigeria and thus requires urgent attention.

Moreover, the sustainability challenges of manufacturing companies in Nigeria extend beyond the environmental concern because being economically viable in the short and long run has become a daunting task for manufacturing companies. Although, Sasu (2022) and Kolawole (2022) suggested that the manufacturing industry contributed 13 per cent to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), with the most significant contribution emanating from the food, beverage, and tobacco sector, which accounted for 4.75 per cent of the total 15.232 trillion Naira GDP. In terms of real GDP, the industry further contributed an average of 6.42 trillion naira to the national GDP for 2019, 2020, and 2021. Yet, the manufacturing sector has struggled to survive over the years due to various challenges that have limited their contributions to the country's GDP.

The relevance of corporate governance to firm sustainability is further bolstered by the stakeholder theory and by how global leaders meet at the worldwide level to engage in discussions on corporate sustainability issues. Similarly, firm-specific factors are internal organizational factors that can enhance firms' performance when deployed appropriately, aligned with the tenet of the resource-based view, which is an inside-out perspective and corroborated by Onamusi et al. (2021). By this discussion, can corporate governance and firm-specific factors be argued to be pivotal to the sustainability of manufacturing companies in Nigeria in the face of the current challenges? We looked through prior studies on sustainability to see whether the question raised has been addressed. We found that sustainability issues have been addressed significantly within developed and emerging economies; however, what remained unexplored is how corporate governance and firm-specific factor interact to influence the sustainability of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The closest literature found was by Suleiman et al. (2021), which established firm-specific factors-sustainability linkage within listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria using secondary data; nevertheless, the study did not consider the boundary condition that brought about the firm-specific factors-sustainability linkage. Likewise, the study did not establish governance as critical to addressing

sustainability nor provided the two-fold relevance of environmental dynamism. This gap in the literature suggests that nothing concrete is known about these interactions, hence the need for this study.

Literature Review

Concept of Sustainability, Corporate Governance, Firm-Specific Factors, and Environmental Dynamism

Corporate sustainability requires firms to maintain a certain level of activity over time. In a broader term, it defines the ability of an entity to continuously meet current goals without jeopardizing the ability of future generations to meet theirs. Sustainability, as it relates to the corporate world, is balanced on three fundamental pillars (economic, social, & environmental), with the understanding that if any of these pillars are missing, then the sustainability of the entity concerned is threatened (Suleiman, Oyedokun, & Adeolu-Akande, 2021).

Corporate governance refers to the manner organizations are directed and controlled in alignment with the interest of diverse stakeholders (Oyedokun, 2019). The adoption of appropriate corporate governance enhanced the sustainable going-concern of organizations and appraised to assure investors of the efficiency of the firm leadership in running the affairs of an organization (Setyahdi & Narsa, 2020), as well as enhancement of business prosperity (Zinkni, 2019), and incline organizations towards sustainable practices (E-Vahdati, 2018).

Firm-specific factors are those resources and capabilities of the firm that bears relevance to deciding the course of action. The ideal firm size is that size that promotes efficiency (Sindhuja, n.d.), and is considered a significant factor in the determination of a firm's profitability (Gaio & Henriques, 2018). The efficient operation of a firm is critical to achieving the highest level of performance using available resources to meet set goals (Banton, 2022). Thus, the adoption of an appropriate firm-specific factor strategy, therefore, can be seen to enhance firm sustainability.

From the conceptual provision, a dynamic environment is characterized by frequent changes in the level of technology, product preference, competition, etc. Thus, it presents threats and opportunities to firms as they adapt to these changes by rejigging corporate strategies in the face of distorted projected profits to ensure the business is sustained (Petrus, 2019).

Theory and Rationale for the Hypothesis

The link between corporate governance, Firm-Specific Factors, Environmental Dynamism, and firm sustainability derived its explanation from the assumptions of the Stakeholders Theory (ST), Resource-based view (RBV), and Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT). ST emphasizes the need for firms to recognize the right of those who have a stake in their existence and, by so doing, enjoy harmonious and more sustainable success. This theory has since become a key concept in the debate of business ethics, arguing against theories that mainly focus on shareholder wealth maximization as a

primary objective of a firm (Freeman, 2018). ST acknowledges that the going concern of an organization can be impacted by those who are either affected by the organization's activities or/and can affect the organization's activities by their actions or inactions - therefore, advocates for firms to factor in the interest of stakeholders into their plans and strategies. The relevance of corporate governance to firm sustainability in this study derives its strength from the ST.

The RBV provides that an organization is made up of various resources which are both tangible and intangible (such as Knowledge, skills, experience, technology, information, and data). The combination of these resources gives birth to other specialized resources (Capabilities), which either individually or collectively create strategic capabilities that provide a sustainable competitive advantage to the organization (Kor, Mahoney, Siemens & Tan, 2016; Onamusi, 2021). This suggestion of the RBV offers support to the relevance of firm-specific factors to firm sustainability in this study.

Following the shortcoming of the RBV in explaining how firms could establish sustained performance in the ever-changing environment, the DCT was employed to bridge this gap, thus replacing the RBV in establishing the relevance of firm-specific factors and environmental dynamism to the sustainability of firms (in this case, FMCG manufacturers in Nigeria). The DCT accentuates the need for a firm to be adaptive, absorptive, and innovative to mitigate the impact of turbulence in the business environment (Onamusi, 2021). The adaptive assumption considers the need for a firm to swiftly organize its resources to address unprecedented environmental changes without distorting organizational performance levels. The innovative capability addresses the need for the firm to bring in new ideas that translate to new products and processes. The absorptive capability centres on the ability of the firm to identify, acquire and utilize external Knowledge to its favour (Kaur & Mehata, 2017).

The central ideas of the ST, RBV, and DCT explain the interaction between the variables of this study. On the strength of the above discussion, this study hypothesized that corporate governance and firm-specific factors are corporate requirements for achieving firm sustainability. However, the relevance of corporate governance to sustainability is enhanced by considering environmental dynamism. Lastly, the relevance of firm-specific factors to sustainability is explained by taking advantage of the growth potential in environmental dynamism.

Empirical Review

Corporate Governance and Sustainability

Various dimensions of corporate governance and their influence on sustainable development have been investigated in different parts of the world. In a systematic literature review to examine the integration of corporate governance with sustainability, the findings disclosed that the interaction between corporate governance and sustainability is interpreted differently in different jurisdictions. Notably, the study also established that leadership, vision, and mission are the most significant drivers of sustainability framework in corporate governance. Also, the sustainability framework provides diverse options that aid in improving organizational efficiency (E-Vahdati, Zulkifi & Zakariya, 2018).

Firm-Specific Factors and Sustainability

Suleiman, Oyedokun and Adeolu-Akande (2021) investigated the impact of firm-specific factors on the sustainability of listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria, using secondary data. The findings show that while firm size exerted a positive and significant effect on the firm's social performance (CSR), fit size and operational efficiency exerted a negative and significant effect on the firm's economic performance (profitability). Furthermore, operational efficiency was found to have no impact on the social performance of the firms. In a different context, an indication of the effect of firm size on environmental performance was established in a study conducted by Ammer, Alieden and Alyahyu (2020). The study focused on listed firms on the TASI index (of Saudi Arabia); the study found a strong positive correlation between environmental performance and firm size, which indicates that large firms are inclined to engage in good environmental practices. This result corroborates the findings of another study conducted to establish the impact of firm characteristics on environmental sustainability. The study reviewed related research conducted in the last 25 years (1996-2020) to develop a comprehensive understanding of organizational characteristics and their implication on environmental sustainability by analyzing the content of 68 relevant articles conducted in 25 countries across America, Europe, Asia, and Africa. The study concluded that larger firms perform better in environmental practices than small firms (Balasubramanian, Shukla, Mangla & Chanchaichuit, 2020). In an earlier study, Andries & Stephan (2019) also reported that larger firms are found to benefit from environmental performance when driven by regulation or industry code of conduct, while environmental performance relates positively with the smaller firms when it is performed as a result of demand from customers.

The intervening effect of environmental dynamism empirical studies on the relevance of environmental dynamism to corporate sustainability have been documented by a few studies. Li, Chen, Ma, and Li (2021) in China, investigated the relationship between Chief Executive Officers empowering leadership and corporate entrepreneurship; the study also extends its tentacles to cover the mediating role of information elaboration in top management teams as well as the moderating role of environmental dynamism. The study found that environmental dynamism positively moderates the relationship between empowering leadership and information collaboration. However, it was found to moderate the relationship between information collaboration and corporate entrepreneurship negatively.

Methodology

The population of the study comprised five thousand, seven hundred and ten (5,710) staff of six (6) registered Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs) manufacturers with their head office in Lagos State, Nigeria (Nestle Nigeria Plc., Procter & Gamble, PZ Cussons, Unilever Nigeria Plc., Cadbury, and Friesland Campina WAMCO Nigeria Plc). The population was obtained from the company's human resource unit as of 21st November, 2021. The FMCGs manufacturers selected are all registered firms that account for more than 85% of Nigeria's consumer goods industry market share. The choice of Lagos State as the geographical setting for this study is because 70% of the FMCG

manufacturers have their head offices in the State (Euromonitor International, 2022). The study adopted the cross-sectional survey design as it attempts to study a subset of a population at a point in time and to investigate the effect of corporate governance and firm-specific factors on the sustainability of fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in Nigeria. The sample size was computed using the Raosoft online sample size calculator for a finite population. From the Raosoft calculator, 360 is considered appropriate for a population of 5,710 employees. The decision is reached at a 5% margin of error critical to management studies and a 95% level of confidence. To address the issue of anticipated non-response, 20% (72) of the sample size was added to the computed sample of 360. The addition of the 72 is to address issues of anticipated non-response from the respondents, and this procedure is in concomitance with existing literature (Onamusi, 2021). In addition, it will ensure that the scientifically determined sample (optimum sample size) is achieved at the end of the study. Therefore, the sample for the staff of selected FMCG manufacturers in Nigeria is 432.

A structured questionnaire was adopted as the study instrument. A total of four hundred and thirty-two (432) copies of the questionnaire were administered by the researcher with the help of research assistants who put concerted efforts to regularly visit the respondents to request them to fill out the instrument, sometimes to clarify queries from the respondents and to prompt the respondents to fill out the questionnaire. Four hundred and six (406) copies were returned. After sorting the questionnaires, 383 copies were certified as duly filled and considered usable. The useable questionnaire represented an 88.65% response rate. Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) was adopted using the SmartPLS version 4.0 to test the hypotheses formulated in this study.

In all, three (3) null hypotheses were tested to meet the objectives of the study. Specifically, the joint effect of corporate governance and firm-specific factors on firm sustainability was examined; the moderating effect of environmental dynamism on the interaction between corporate governance and firm sustainability was determined, and the mediating effect of environmental dynamism in the interaction between firm-specific factors and firm sustainability was examined.

Results

Validity and Reliability

The validity and reliability of the instrument were carried out using the PLS-SEM algorithm. Measures of statistical validity and reliability carried out include Cronbach's Alpha coefficient (CA), Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and Discriminant Validity via the PLS-SEM method. The statistics for the validity and reliability test carried out were found to be higher than the minimum required; thus, the instrument was judged to be valid and reliable. The result of the test is shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Validity and Reliability Test for Measured Items

Variables		CA	CR	AVE
Corporate Governance	Accountability	0.655	0.679	0.435
	Agile Leadership	0.644	0.809	0.591
	Stakeholder management	0.729	0.782	0.485
Firm-specific factors	Firm size	0.647	0.711	0.474
	Operational efficiency	0.847	0.886	0.568
Sustainability	Environmental performance	0.953	0.960	0.729
	Profitability	0.683	0.792	0.530
	Corporate social responsibility	0.790	0.859	0.554
Intervening variable	Environmental dynamism	0.813	0.870	0.579

Source: Researcher's Result via SmartPLS V.4.0 (2023)

Table 2: Discriminant Validity using Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Construct	ACT	AGL	CSR	EVD	ENV	FS	OE	PRT	SUS
Accountability									
Agile Leadership	0.9								
Corporate social responsibility	0.77	0.46							
Environmental dynamism	0.48	0.69	0.98						
Environmental performance	0.61	0.91	0.57	0.83					
Firm size	0.79	0.67	0.58	0.65	0.55				
Operational efficiency	0.53	0.8	0.31	0.65	0.59	0.54			
Profitability	0.9	0.99	0.7	0.74	0.99	0.81	0.8		
Stakeholder management	0.43	0.57	0.68	0.44	0.52	0.67	0.38	0.87	

Source: Researcher's Result via SmartPLS V.0.4 (2023)

The result of the convergent and divergent validity is presented in Table 1 and that of the discriminant validity is presented in Table 2. AVE's value greater than 0.5 provided added proof of convergent validity, and the discriminate validity value for all the constructs below 1.00 on the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) criterion provided additional evidence of construct validity for each of the measured variables. Both the AVE and discriminant validity values provided evidence of construct validity for all the variables under study. Furthermore, the reliability test is shown in Table 1. The result of the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient (CA) which is revalidated using the Composite Reliability (CR) is within the accepted benchmark of > 0.7 but < 1 score. Therefore, the instrument is deemed reliable.

Sustainability Testing

H₀₁ Corporate governance and firm-specific factors have no significant effect on the sustainability performance of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂ Environmental dynamism has no significant moderating effect on the effect of corporate governance on the sustainability performance of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃ Environmental dynamism has no significant mediating effect on the effect of firm-specific factors on the sustainability performance of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

To test the direct, moderation, and mediation hypothesis, PLS-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) was adopted using the SmartPLS statistical platform version 4.0. The independent variable is corporate governance and firm-specific factors, sustainability constitutes the dependent variable and environmental dynamism is the intervening variable.

Table 3: Summary of PLS-SEM Analysis for the Direct, Moderation and Mediation effect of environmental dynamism on the interaction between corporate governance, firm-specific factors and sustainability of selected FMCG Manufacturers in Nigeria

Path Coefficient	Original Sample(O)	Sample Mean(M)	T-Statistics	P-Values	Q ²
Model 1,2					
Corporate Governance → Sustainability	0.540	0.544	3.739	0.000	
Environmental dynamism → Sustainability	0.585	0.463	3.636	0.000	0.099
Firm-specific factors → Environmental dynamism	0.678	0.728	4.317	0.001	
Firm-specific factors → Sustainability	-0.126	-0.010	0.865	0.388	
CG*ENV → Sustainability	0.386	0.263	2.741	0.006	0.290
Specific Indirect Effect					
FSF → ENV → Sustainability	0.396	0.332	2.919	0.004	
	R ²	Adj. R ²			
Corporate governance and Firm-specific factor → Sustainability	0.889	0.878		0.000	

Note: CG- Corporate Governance, FSF- Firm-specific Factor, ENV- Environmental Dynamism

Source: Researchers' Results via SmartPLS V4.0 (2023)

The PLS-SEM result in Table 3 indicated that, corporate governance and firm-specific factor jointly have a significant effect on the sustainability of the selected FMCG manufacturers in Nigeria. Specifically, the adjusted coefficient of determination (*Adj R²*) of 0.878 showed that corporate governance and firm-specific factor predicted 87.8% of the changes in sustainability while the remaining 11.1% of changes in sustainability is explained by external factors different from variables considered in this study and the effect is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval and p-value less than 0.05.

In addition, Figures 2, 3, 4, and Table 3 present the results of PLS-SEM analysis for the intervening (moderation-mediation) effect of environmental dynamism on the interaction between corporate governance, firm-specific factors, and sustainability of the selected FMCG companies in Nigeria.

First to establish the moderating effect in a PLS-SEM warrants the creation of a new variable termed corporate governance *environmental dynamism. This interaction term's influence is examined on the dependent variable (Sustainability) and a significant moderating effect is established if the coefficient of the interaction term has a p-value less than 0.05. It is noteworthy that in a moderation PLS-SEM analysis, emphasis is on the moderating path result and with less attention to Adj R² or the R² coefficient found in SPSS output for moderation analysis. From the result in Figures 2, 3, 4 and Table 3, it is observed that the interaction term of corporate governance*environmental dynamism has a path coefficient of determination value of 0.386. This suggests that the introduction of environmental dynamism has enhanced the effect corporate governance has on sustainability by 0.386 and this moderating effect is positive and statistically significant at p-value = 0.006.

Further analysis in Figures 2, 3, 4 and Table 3, presents the results of PLS-SEM analysis for the mediating effect of environmental dynamism on the interaction between firm-specific factors and sustainability of the selected FMCG manufacturing companies in Nigeria. To establish the mediating effect in PLS-SEM, the study followed the preconditions prescribed by a researcher; According to Baron and Kenny (1986), full mediation occurs when the direct interaction between an independent variable (firm-specific factors) and the dependent variable (Sustainability) becomes insignificant at the introduction of a third variable (environmental dynamism) considered a mediator. In addition to Baron and Kenny, PLS-SEM via the SmartPLS offers the result for the specific indirect effect examined. The specific indirect effects from 'Firm-specific factors' → 'Environmental dynamism' → 'Sustainability' must be statistically significant (Adeyemo et al., 2022). If the impact is a full mediation, then the direct impact of firm-specific factors on the sustainability of the selected FMCGs companies in Nigeria from the path analysis will be statistically insignificant. However, if the indirect effect and the direct effects are significant from the path analysis then a partial mediation is established.

Given the above precondition, the PLS-SEM result in Figures 2, 3, 4, and Table 3 shows that the direct path (influence) from Firm-specific factors to Sustainability of FMCGs firms is statistically insignificant ($\beta = -0.126$, $t = 0.865$, $p = 0.388$). The path from Firm-specific factors to environmental dynamism is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.678$, $t = 4.317$, $p = 0.000$). Lastly, the path from environmental dynamism to the sustainability of the selected FMCG manufacturers is statistically significant ($\beta = 0.585$, $t = 3.636$, $p = 0.000$). The implication of this result (in relation to the preconditions for the presence of mediation as postulated by scholars suggests that since the specific indirect effect (Firm-specific factors → environmental dynamism → operation performance) is significant across all the paths (see Table 3), then the study provides evidence to establish a mediating impact. More specifically, because the direct impact of Firm-specific factors on sustainability is insignificant while the specific indirect path 'Firm-specific factors → environmental dynamism → operation performance' is significant, hence a full mediating effect is established. In other words, the result posits that the

impact firm-specific factors have on sustainability is a result of environmental dynamism. More specifically, the effect firm-specific factors have on the sustainability of the selected FMCGs companies in Nigeria is explained by taking advantage of opportunities in a dynamic environment.

In addition, the PLS-SEM provides the result of the specific indirect effect to reinforce the mediation analysis threshold positioned. According to Table 3, the result of the specific indirect effect shows a path analysis from Firm-specific factors → environmental dynamism → sustainability ($\beta=0.396$, $t=2.919$, $p=0.004$) proves that, as a whole, the indirect path is significant. On the strength of the moderated analysis ($\beta=0.386$; $p<0.006$, $Q^2=0.290$) and the mediation analysis ($\beta=0.396$, $t=2.919$, $p=0.004$, $Q^2=0.099$), this study can conclude that environmental dynamism has two-folds relevance acting as a significant moderator between corporate governance-sustainability linkage and equally serving as the boundary condition (a full mediator) that explain the linkage between firm-specific factors and sustainability of the selected FMCGs companies in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study investigated how corporate governance and firm-specific factors aid the Sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Nigeria. It also evaluated the role of environmental dynamism as a moderator between corporate governance and sustainability and the mediating role of environmental dynamism between firm-specific factors and the sustainability of the FCMG manufacturers.

The result of the PLS-SEM shows that corporate governance and firm-specific factors jointly exerted a positive and significant effect on the Sustainability of FMCG manufacturers in Nigeria. A dearth of empirical works of literature has attempted to investigate the combined effect of corporate governance and firm-specific factors either by interrogating the measures used in this study or through other relevant dimensions. Nevertheless, the findings on the effect of corporate governance on Sustainability found support for previous empirical studies, such as Utami et al. (2020); Maali, Rakia and Khaireddine (2021); Antwi-Adjei, et al (2020); and Lazaroiu et al. (2020). The study findings provide support for the stakeholder theory perspective, which affirms that firms that are interested in sustainability need to factor the interest of stakeholders into their plans and policies to ensure that a harmonious relationship is established and maintained with these diverse stakeholders, given that these stakeholders can be impacted by the firm activities and firm activities can as well be impacted by these stakeholders' actions. This study's results are in concomitance with these theoretical perspectives.

In line with the findings of this study, therefore, the potency of the effect of corporate governance on sustainability is contingent on environmental dynamism. Therefore, on the strength of the dynamic capability theory, this study posits that while corporate governance is found to be pivotal to corporate sustainability, the dynamic environment within which the fast-moving consumer goods manufacturing companies operate in Nigeria increases the potency of the relevance of cooperate governance to the sustainable operation and performance of the FMCG manufacturers in Nigeria.

Finally, the findings of this study showed that environmental dynamism also serves as a boundary condition (full mediator) that explains the linkage between firm-specific factors and the sustainability of the FMCG manufacturers in Nigeria.

By implication, the dynamic nature of the external environment dictates the extent to which a firm adapts to business realities to survive (Andrade & Mendez, 2019). In line with the findings of this study, the relevance of firm-specific factors to the sustainability of the FMCG manufacturers in Nigeria lies in the opportunities and growth potential presented in the dynamic environment, as presented by Onamusi et al. (2019). This means that in the absence of the firm's capacity to take advantage of environmental munificence, it becomes less significant for firm-specific factors to determine the sustainability performance of FMCG manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Thus, the finding of this study gives sustenance to the dynamic capability theory, which emphasizes the need to factor in the dynamic nature of the business environment within which organizations operate in order to generate a sustainable competitive edge. Kaur and Mehata (2017) corroborated the submission of DCT to stress that a swift organization of resources to address unprecedented environmental changes, bringing in new ideas that translate to new products and processes, identification, acquisition, and utilization of external Knowledge is critical for a firm competitive advantage.

References

- Adeyemo, K., Adie, C., & Onamusi, A. (2022). Implementation of transfer pricing regulations should improve tax revenue growth in Nigeria. Is this true? Does institutional capacity have a Role? *International Journal of Advances Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*, 2(6), 2022, 623-631.
- Ammer, M. A., Alieden, M. M., & Alyahyu, M. A. (2020). Do corporate environmental sustainability practices influence firm value? The role of independent directors: Evidence from Saudi Arabia. *MDPI*, 12(22), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12229768>
- Andrade, J., Franco, M., & Mendez, L. (2019). Technology capacity and organizational ambidexterity: The moderating role of environmental dynamism on Portuguese technological SMEs. *Review of Managerial Science*, 15(7), 2019, 2111-2136.
- Andries, P., & Stephan, U. (2019). Environmental innovation and firm performance: How Firm size and motives matter. *MDPI*, 11(13), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11133585>
- Antwi-Adjei, A., Kong, Y., Kwame, O., & Antwi-Adjei, N. A. (2020). A review: Corporate governance and sustainability. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, 7(6), 79-89. <https://doi.org/10.32628/IJSRST20769>
- Asihkia, O.U., Adewole, A.A., Onamusi A.B., & Makinde, G.O. (2022). The affinity to execute strategy could drive firm profitability. Is this true? What role does an agile leader play? *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: A Administration and Management*, 22(5), 48-62.
- Balasubramanian, S., Shukla, V., Mangla, S., & Chanchaichuit, J. (2020). Do firm characteristics affect environmental sustainability? A literature review-based assessment. *Business strategy and environmental*, 30(2), 1389-1416. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2692>

- Banton, C. (2022, June 02). *Efficiency definition*. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/e/efficiency.asp>
- Baron, M., & Kenny, D.A. (1986). The moderating variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173-1182.
- Chen, X., Jiang, G. Yang, L., & Xiang, F. (2020). Redesign of enterprise lean production system based on environmental dynamism. *Wiley Online Library*, 32(14). <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.5706>
- Euromonitor International (2022, 7th May). *Lagos in Nigeria*. <https://www.euromonitor.com/lagos-in-nigeria/report>
- E-Vahdati, S., Zulkifli, N., & Zakaria, Z. (2018). A moderated mediation model for board diversity and corporate performance in ASEAN countries. *MDPI*, 10(2), 556. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10020556>.
- E-Vahdati, S., Zulkifli, N., & Zakaria, Z. (2019). Corporate governance integration with Sustainability: A systematic literature review. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*. 19(2), 255-269. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-03-2018-0111>
- Freeman, E. R. (2018). *About the Stakeholder Theory*. Stakeholder Theory. <http://stakeholdertheory.org/about/>
- Gaio, C., & Henriques, R. (2018). Are Large firms more profitable than small and medium firms in the European Union? *European Journal of Management Studies*, 23(1), 25-48.
- Kaur, V., & Mehta, V. (2017). Dynamic capability for competitive advantage: A comparative study of IT multinationals in India. *Sage*, 21(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0971890717701781>
- Kolawole, Y. (2022, May 9). *Contribution to economy: Manufacturing sector stagnates*. Vanguard. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2022/05/gdp-contribution-to-economy-manufacturing-sectorstagnates/#:~:text=A%20breakdown%20of%20the%20NBS,percent%20and%208.98%20percent%2C%20respectively>
- Kor, Y.Y., Mahoney, T.J., Siemsen, E., & Tan, D. (2016). Penrose's the theory of the growth of the firm: An exemplar of engaged scholarship. *Production and operations management*. 25(10), 1727-1744. <https://doi.org/10.1111/poms.12572>
- Lazaroiu, G., Ionescu, L., Andronie, M., & Dijmarescu, I. (2020). Sustainability management in the urban corporate economy: A systematic literature review. *MDPI*, 12(18), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12187705>
- Li, Z., Chen, H. Ma, Q., & Li, H. (2021). CEO empowering leadership and corporate entrepreneurship: The roles of TMT information elaboration and environmental dynamism. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 1-15.
- Maali, K., Rakia, R., & Khairiddine, M. (2021). How corporate social responsibility mediates the relationship between corporate governance and sustainability performance in UK: a multiple mediator analysis. *Society and business review*. 16(2), 201-217. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SBR-12-2020-0143>.

- Onamusi A. B., Umokoro J., Ibronke, O. E., & Babatope, V. (2022). Twofold innovation behaviour and *Omoluabi* leadership: Surviving COVID-19 pandemic through unlearning effect. *Innovation* 71, 583-598.
- Onamusi A.B., Asihkia, O.U., & Makinde, G.O. (2019). Environmental munificence and service firm performance: The moderating role of management innovation capability. *Business Management Dynamics* 9(6), 13-25.
- Onamusi, A. B. (2021). Adaptive capability, social media agility, ambidextrous marketing capability, and business survival: A mediation analysis. *Marketing and Branding Research*, 8(1), 31-47.
- Onamusi, A. B. (2021). Entry mode strategy and firm performance in emerging economy: Moderating role of organizational structure and environmental turbulence. *Journal of Sustainable Business and Management Solutions in Emerging Economies*, 26(1), 1-8.
- Onamusi, A. B., Adenekan, T. E., Ojo, E. O., & Owolabi, O. A. (2021). Firm-specific capability, organizational structure, and new product performance of fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in emerging economy. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*, 3(1), in press
- Oyedokun, G.E. (2019). *Business policy: Strategy, governance, risk and ethics*. Aaron & Hur Publishing.
- Petrus, B. (2019). Environmental dynamism: The implication for operational and dynamic capabilities. *Management Sciences*, 24(1), 2019, 28-36.
- Setyahdi, R.R., & Narsa, M. I. (2020). Corporate governance and Sustainability in Indonesia, *Journal of Asian Finance, Economic and Business*, 7(12), 2020, 885-894. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no12.885>
- Sindhuja, S. (n.d.). *The Size of a Firm: Definitions, Measures and Concepts*. Business Management Ideas, <https://www.businessmanagementideas.com/enterprises/the-size-of-a-firm-definition-measures-and-concepts/9054>
- Suleiman, M.A., Oyedokun, G. E., & Adeolu-Akande, M. A. (2021). Firm-specific factors and sustainability of listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Global Research Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 2(1), 65-79.
- Utami, H.N., Cahyana, E.B., Nimran, U., & Iqbal, M. (2020). Organizational transformation as a determinant of corporate hospitality and its effect on corporate sustainability. *International Trade, Politics and Development*, 4(2), 105-125. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITPD-04-2020-0014>
- Wendling, Z., Esty, D. C., & Sherbinin, A. (2019). Environmental performance index 2020. Yale Center for Environmental Law & Policy. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21182.51529>
- Zhang, J. A., O'Kane, C., & Chen, G. (2020). Business ties, political ties, and innovation performance in Chinese industrial firms: The role of entrepreneurial orientation and environmental dynamism. *Journal of Business Research*, 121(c), 254-267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.08.055>
- Zinkni, J. (2019). *Better governance across the board: Creating value through reputation, people, and processes*, Boston: De Gruyter.